

TESTDISK And PHOTOREC – Analysis and Comparison

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Abstract: In the modern world there is a data for everything. Data has become an important part of life. It could be an official data, personal data, student data, super mart data or whatever. Along with data, data recovery these days has become a very important part of everyday life. Data recovery comes under forensic science. Data that is either deleted or corrupted sometimes need to be recovered. For recovering of deleted data, that has been deleted accidentally or intentionally, there are many tools available in the market. In this paper we have mentioned the top two tools of data discovery.

Key Words: Data recovery, TESTDISK, PhotoRec,

I. INTRODUCTION

Data recovery is a process of extracting deleted, corrupted or damaged data from secondary storage devices, removable media or files when it cannot be recovered in normal way. Data is derived from a variety of storage devices, including hard drives, USB drives, CDs, and other electronic devices. Physical damage to the storage can necessitate recovery. The file system has been damaged physically or logically, preventing it from being mounted by the host operating system (OS). 'The' an operating system failure, a storage device malfunction, or an accident are the most common reasons for data recovery. Users would not be able to find deleted files using a regular file manager, but the data is still present on the disc. Meanwhile, the original file contents can be recoverable, often in a number of disconnected fragments. In the context of forensic software, the expression "data recovery" is often used. Orespionage, in which data that has been encrypted or hidden is retrieved rather than compromised [5].

II. DATA RECOVERY TOOLS

TestDisk is a data recovery programme that is both free and open-source[1]. It is mainly intended to assist in the recovery of missing data storage partitions and/or the re-

booting of non-booting discs when these symptoms are triggered by faulty applications, viruses, or human error (such as accidentally erasing a partition table)[3]. It can be used to gather comprehensive information about a corrupted disc, which can then be used to repair the drive.

PhotoRec is a file data recovery tool that can be used to retrieve missing files such as video, documents, and archives from hard drives, CD-ROMs, and lost photos (hence the name Photo Recovery) from digital camera memory[2]. PhotoRec works even if the media's file system has been badly corrupted or reformatted because it ignores the file system and goes after the underlying data[3].

PhotoRec is a companion programme to TestDisk, a programme that recovers missing partitions on a variety of file systems and re-boots non-bootable discs. Hard discs, CD-ROMs, memory cards, USB memory drives, DD raw image, EnCase E01 image, and so on are all supported by PhotoRec.

We can solve TestDisk's limitations and recover all missing data from any file system by combining TestDisk and PhotoRec. We may also recover data from CD-ROMs, memory cards, and other storage devices. This study aims to combine the above-mentioned tools for successful data recovery while avoiding the drawbacks, as well as compare and contrast both tools.

III. IMPLEMENTATION

STEPS

Getting TestDisk

While it is a Linux utility, you don't actually have to have Linux *installed* to use it

Figure 6: You can select the files using “:” command and copy the files clicking on” C”

Figure 8: After choosing the destination folder click on “C” to copy the file. The file will be copied to destination.

Figure 7: After that it will ask you to select the destination folder to copy the files.

photoRec

Figure 9: Under Kali Linux you need to be root to run PhotoRec (ie. sudo testdisk-6.13/photorec_static) Disk selection

Figure 10: Source partition selection

Figure 12: File system type

Figure 11: Selection of files to recover

Figure 13: Curve the part

Figure 14: Select where recovered files should be written

Figure 15: Recovery is completed

IV. COMPARISON

The tools described above have many different features. Some of the features are same for all the tools and some are different. Comparisons of few of the common features of the tools described above have been done in the Table 1 below

Tools	FILE SYSTEM		COMMAND LINE	GUI
	FAT	NTFS		
TESTDISK	✓	✓	✓	✗
PHOTOREC	✓	✓	✓	✗

Table 1

V. CONCLUSION

The basic function of the tools mentioned above is to restore or recover the accidentally or intentionally deleted files from the system. The tools mentioned above are the top fine tools of file recovery. Both are command line tools. Photo Rec and Test disk is companion program. All of these tools have different working and features but the purpose is the same. The common thing about these tools are they work with both FAT, NTFS file system. In future we will try to work on the tools and find out which tool has the better performance in recovery of deleted files from the system.

VI. REFERENCES

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